

Black holes in Bumblebee gravity with dual topological defects: Geodesic structure and thermodynamics

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We investigate the geodesic structure, optical response, and thermodynamic fluctuations of a Schwarzschild-like black hole solution in bumblebee gravity in the presence of two topological defects: a global monopole and a cloud of strings. Working directly with the effective line element, we derive the null and timelike geodesic equations and analyze circular photon orbits, critical impact parameters, weak-field deflection, shadow relations, observational shadow constraints, and the innermost stable circular orbit (ISCO). We then formulate the thermodynamics using a properly normalized Killing time at infinity, obtaining the Hawking temperature, entropy, the first-law-compatible thermodynamic energy, the heat capacity, and the Helmholtz free energy in the normalized frame. Finally, we examine thermodynamic fluctuations through Ruppeiner information geometry by allowing the monopole scale to fluctuate macroscopically while keeping the string-cloud sector fixed. The first-law-compatible two-parameter state space has a nontrivial scalar curvature, which is negative in the physical domain and does not develop a finite degeneracy locus. We comment on the importance of using the energy conjugate to the normalized Killing time and on possible extensions in which additional thermodynamic variables, such as charge or pressure, are promoted to fluctuating degrees of freedom.

I. INTRODUCTION

The detection of gravitational waves and the imaging of horizon-scale black-hole shadows have provided strong evidence in favor of General Relativity (GR), yet the search for consistent ultraviolet completions and the possibility of low-energy imprints of quantum-gravity-inspired effects remain central themes in modern gravitational physics. One of the best-motivated effective frameworks to parametrize departures from exact local Lorentz invariance is the Standard-Model Extension (SME), which provides a systematic effective-field-theory language for matter and gravity sectors with Lorentz-violating coefficients [1–4]. In the gravitational sector, Lorentz symmetry breaking may arise spontaneously, and the simplest realizations are commonly referred to as bumblebee models, in which a vector field acquires a nonzero vacuum expectation value and induces Lorentz-violating corrections to gravitational dynamics [1, 5–15]. Exact and effective black-hole solutions in such scenarios have stimulated a broad literature on geodesic motion, perturbations, shadows, Hawking radiation, and related phenomenology [11, 16–23].

On the other hand, spontaneously broken symmetries in the early universe may also produce stable relics such as global monopoles, cosmic strings, and string-cloud configurations. These topological defects imprint angular deficits and modify light propagation and particle dynamics in black-hole spacetimes [24–29]. Motivated by these considerations, it is natural to explore black-hole geometries where Lorentz-violating

effects coexist with defects, and to determine how such ingredients deform classical observables such as photon spheres, ISCO radii, weak-field lensing, and shadow observables, as well as how they affect thermodynamic response and fluctuations. Related studies of modified black-hole optical signatures, greybody factors, and strong/weak lensing in non-Schwarzschild backgrounds provide useful benchmarks for this analysis [30–38]. Closely related recent works by Ahmed and Silva have examined Letelier/string-cloud black holes and Lorentz-violating black holes with string-cloud or monopole sectors, including their geodesics, shadows, thermodynamics, and phase structure [23, 39, 40].

In this work we focus on the geodesic dynamics and thermodynamic fluctuations of a Schwarzschild-like bumblebee black hole endowed with two defect contributions: (i) a global monopole characterized by the symmetry-breaking scale η [27], and (ii) a cloud of strings governed by a constant α [28, 41–43]. In order to keep the present preprint sharply focused on geodesics and thermodynamic fluctuations, we take as input the effective line element available in the literature (see, e.g., [11, 19, 44] for the bumblebee-sector construction) and incorporate the two defects through an effective deficit parameter. This allows us to bypass the field-equation derivation (not needed for our purposes) and to concentrate on the physical consequences.

The present study also connects with the thermodynamic interpretation of black holes, which began with the area law and Hawking temperature and has since been extended to Euclidean methods, entropy corrections, extended phase spaces, and geometric descriptions of thermodynamic fluctuations [45–53]. In particular, Weinhold and Ruppeiner geometries have become standard tools for diagnosing the microstructure and stability of black-hole ensembles [54–61]. These tools are especially useful here because the monopole parameter enters nonlinearly and can be promoted to a macroscopic fluctuation

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coordinate.

This paper is organized as follows. In Sec. II we present the effective metric and define the physical parameter domain. In Sec. III we derive the geodesic structure, including orbital equations, the photon sphere, weak deflection, shadow relations, EHT-motivated bounds, and the ISCO. In Sec. IV we develop the thermodynamics using an asymptotically normalized Killing time. In Sec. V we study thermodynamic fluctuations via information geometry using the thermodynamic energy selected by the first law. We conclude in Sec. VI. Technical derivations are collected in the appendices.

II. EFFECTIVE METRIC WITH DUAL TOPOLOGICAL DEFECTS

We consider a static and spherically symmetric Schwarzschild-like geometry in bumblebee gravity with a Lorentz-violating parameter $\ell \geq 0$, and two defect contributions associated with a global monopole and a cloud of strings. The Schwarzschild-like radial deformation follows the bumblebee black-hole constructions discussed in Refs. [11, 15, 19, 44], while the angular-deficit sector is modeled in the spirit of the global-monopole and string-cloud geometries of Refs. [27, 28]. The effective line element is taken as [44]

$$ds^2 = -f(r) dt^2 + \frac{1+\ell}{f(r)} dr^2 + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2), \quad (1)$$

with

$$f(r) = 1 - \Delta - \frac{2M}{r}, \quad \Delta \equiv \alpha + \kappa\eta^2, \quad \kappa = 8\pi. \quad (2)$$

Here M is the mass parameter, η is the symmetry-breaking scale of the global monopole, and α is the cloud-of-strings parameter. The combination Δ acts as an effective deficit parameter. We assume

$$0 \leq \Delta < 1, \quad (3)$$

so that the spacetime is well-defined and admits an event horizon.

The horizon radius follows from $f(r_h) = 0$:

$$r_h = \frac{2M}{1-\Delta}. \quad (4)$$

Figure 1 illustrates the radial metric function entering the effective line element (1). For fixed M and fixed η , the horizon is defined by the largest root of $f(r_h) = 0$, namely Eq. (4). Therefore, increasing α decreases the asymptotic value $f(r \rightarrow \infty) = 1 - \Delta$ and moves the horizon radius to larger r . This behavior summarizes how the defect sector encoded in Δ modifies the redshift factor at infinity; correspondingly, characteristic radii such as the photon sphere and the ISCO inherit the same scaling $\propto (1-\Delta)^{-1}$, while the Lorentz-violating parameter ℓ rescales the radial sector and affects the radial evolution without shifting the locations of the circular orbits in this radial scaling analysis.

Figure 2 illustrates the universal rescaling of the characteristic radii induced by the defect sector through the single combination $\Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$. As Δ increases, the horizon, photon sphere, and ISCO are pushed to larger radii, while their mutual ratios remain unchanged (since all of them scale

FIG. 1. Metric function $f(r) = 1 - \Delta - \frac{2M}{r}$ for representative values of the defect parameter α , with η fixed and $\Delta(\alpha) = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$ (with $\kappa = 8\pi$). The horizontal dashed line indicates $f(r) = 0$, and the vertical dotted lines mark the event-horizon radii $r_h = 2M/[1-\Delta]$ for each α . Increasing α (hence increasing Δ) lowers the asymptotic level $f(r \rightarrow \infty) = 1 - \Delta$ and shifts the horizon outwards.

FIG. 2. Characteristic radii as functions of the effective deficit parameter $\Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$. We show the horizon radius r_h , the photon-sphere radius r_{ph} , and the ISCO radius r_{ISCO} (all in units of M), given respectively by Eqs. (4), (22), and (52). All three radii increase monotonically with Δ and diverge as $\Delta \rightarrow 1^-$.

as $(1-\Delta)^{-1}$ according to Eqs. (4), (22), and (52)). In the strong-deficit regime $\Delta \rightarrow 1^-$, the divergence of these radii signals that the relevant orbital and horizon length scales become arbitrarily large for fixed M , with direct implications for light capture and the location of stable timelike motion.

A. Asymptotic time normalization

Since $g_{tt} \rightarrow -(1 - \Delta)$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$, the coordinate t is not asymptotically normalized, a familiar feature of conical-defect geometries and of global thermodynamic treatments in non-standard asymptotics [27, 28, 46, 53]. For thermodynamic quantities tied to the Killing time, it is convenient to introduce

$$\bar{t} = \sqrt{1 - \Delta} t, \quad (5)$$

so that $g_{\bar{t}\bar{t}} \rightarrow -1$ at infinity. We will use this normalization in Sec. IV. (For purely geometric quantities such as the coordinate location of photon spheres, this rescaling is immaterial.)

III. GEODESIC STRUCTURE

In this section we analyze null and timelike geodesics for the effective line element (1). We work in the equatorial plane $\theta = \pi/2$ without loss of generality, following the standard effective-potential approach to black-hole orbits [22, 30, 31].

A. Constants of motion and radial equation

The geodesic dynamics follows from the Lagrangian $\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}\dot{x}^\mu\dot{x}^\nu$, where dot denotes differentiation with respect to an affine parameter λ . In the equatorial plane $\theta = \pi/2$, the Lagrangian reads

$$2\mathcal{L} = -f(r)\dot{t}^2 + \frac{1+\ell}{f(r)}\dot{r}^2 + r^2\dot{\phi}^2. \quad (6)$$

Stationarity and axial symmetry imply the conserved quantities

$$E \equiv -\frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial\dot{t}} = f(r)\dot{t}, \quad L \equiv \frac{\partial\mathcal{L}}{\partial\dot{\phi}} = r^2\dot{\phi}, \quad (7)$$

so that

$$\dot{t} = \frac{E}{f(r)}, \quad \dot{\phi} = \frac{L}{r^2}. \quad (8)$$

The normalization condition is

$$g_{\mu\nu}\dot{x}^\mu\dot{x}^\nu = -\varepsilon, \quad \varepsilon = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{timelike geodesics,} \\ 0, & \text{null geodesics.} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Substituting (8) into (9), we find the equation of motion of test particles for the radial component as,

$$\dot{r}^2 = V_{\text{eff}}, \quad (10)$$

where the effective potential of the system is defined as

$$V_{\text{eff}} = \frac{1}{1+\ell} \left[E^2 - \left(\varepsilon + \frac{L^2}{r^2} \right) f(r) \right]. \quad (11)$$

Circular orbits are determined by $\dot{r} = 0$ together with $\ddot{r} = 0$.

B. Orbital equations in terms of $u(\phi) = 1/r$

Introducing $u(\phi) \equiv 1/r(\phi)$, we use

$$\frac{dr}{d\lambda} = \frac{dr}{d\phi} \frac{d\phi}{d\lambda}, \quad \frac{d\phi}{d\lambda} = \dot{\phi} = \frac{L}{r^2} = Lu^2. \quad (12)$$

Since $r = 1/u$, we have $\frac{dr}{d\phi} = -(1/u^2) \frac{du}{d\phi}$, and therefore

$$\dot{r} = \frac{dr}{d\lambda} = -\frac{1}{u^2} \frac{du}{d\phi} (Lu^2) = -L \frac{du}{d\phi}. \quad (13)$$

Squaring (13) and substituting into (10) yields

$$L^2 \left(\frac{du}{d\phi} \right)^2 = \frac{1}{1+\ell} [E^2 - f(r) (\varepsilon + L^2 u^2)]. \quad (14)$$

Using $r = 1/u$ and defining

$$f(u) = 1 - \Delta - 2Mu, \quad (15)$$

we obtain the first-order orbital equation

$$\left(\frac{du}{d\phi} \right)^2 = \frac{1}{(1+\ell)L^2} [E^2 - f(u) (\varepsilon + L^2 u^2)]. \quad (16)$$

To obtain a second-order Binet-type equation, differentiate (16) with respect to ϕ and after simplification yields

$$u'' + \frac{1-\Delta}{1+\ell} u = \frac{M\varepsilon}{(1+\ell)L^2} + \frac{3M}{1+\ell} u^2. \quad (17)$$

Therefore, for null geodesics ($\varepsilon = 0$),

$$\frac{d^2u}{d\phi^2} + \frac{1-\Delta}{1+\ell} u = \frac{3M}{1+\ell} u^2, \quad (18)$$

and for timelike geodesics ($\varepsilon = 1$),

$$\frac{d^2u}{d\phi^2} + \frac{1-\Delta}{1+\ell} u = \frac{M}{(1+\ell)L^2} + \frac{3M}{1+\ell} u^2. \quad (19)$$

C. Null geodesics: photon sphere and critical impact parameter

For photons ($\varepsilon = 0$), the effective potential reduces to

$$V_{\text{eff}}^{(\gamma)}(r) = \frac{1}{1+\ell} \left[E^2 - \frac{L^2}{r^2} f(r) \right]. \quad (20)$$

Unstable circular photon orbits define the capture threshold and the high-frequency optical response of compact objects [30, 31, 37]. They satisfy $\frac{dV_{\text{eff}}^{(\gamma)}}{dr} = 0$ (with $L \neq 0$), namely

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{f(r)}{r^2} \right) = 0 \Rightarrow r f'(r) - 2f(r) = 0. \quad (21)$$

With $f(r) = 1 - \Delta - 2M/r$, we have $f'(r) = 2M/r^2$, so (21) after simplification yields the photon sphere radius as,

$$r_{\text{ph}} = \frac{3M}{1-\Delta} = \frac{3M}{1-\alpha-\kappa\eta^2}. \quad (22)$$

In the limit $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, corresponding to the absence of string cloud effects, the photon sphere radius reduces to $r_{\text{ph}} = \frac{3M}{1-\kappa\eta^2}$, which coincides with the result for a black hole

FIG. 3. Effective potentials illustrating the impact of the defect sector when the string-cloud parameter α is varied at fixed monopole scale η (so that $\Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$ with $\kappa = 8\pi$). (Left) Null effective potential per unit L^2 , $V_{\text{eff}}^{(\gamma)}(r)/L^2 = f(r)/r^2$ and $f(r)$, with dotted vertical lines marking the photon-sphere radius r_{ph} . (Right) Timelike effective potential $V_{\text{eff}}^{(m)}(r)$ evaluated at $L = L_{\text{ISCO}}(\alpha)$ (obtained from Eq. (50) at $r = r_{\text{ISCO}}$), with dotted vertical lines indicating r_{ISCO} . In both panels, increasing α increases the effective deficit $\Delta(\alpha)$ and therefore shifts the characteristic radii according to the universal scaling $(1 - \Delta)^{-1}$, while also lowering the overall potential scale through the factor $f(r) = 1 - \Delta - 2M/r$.

with a global monopole [27]. When $\eta = 0$, representing the absence of global monopole effects, the photon sphere radius becomes $r_{\text{ph}} = \frac{3M}{1-\alpha}$, in agreement with the Letelier black hole solution [28]. Finally, in the simultaneous absence of both defects ($\alpha = 0$ and $\eta = 0$), the standard Schwarzschild photon sphere is recovered, $r_{\text{ph}} = 3M$.

Figure 3 provides a direct visualization of how the defect sector, encoded in the effective deficit parameter $\Delta(\alpha)$, deforms the geodesic dynamics through the effective potentials. For null geodesics, the maximum of $V_{\text{eff}}^{(\gamma)}(r)/L^2$ identifies the unstable circular photon orbit and hence the capture threshold; correspondingly, the peak location tracks the photon-sphere radius r_{ph} as α is increased. For timelike motion, evaluating $V_{\text{eff}}^{(m)}(r)$ at $L = L_{\text{ISCO}}(\alpha)$ highlights the marginal stability: the transition between stable configurations (admitting a local minimum for radii above r_{ISCO}) and unstable behavior below it occurs at a radius that is pushed outward as $\Delta(\alpha)$ grows.

The critical impact parameter $b_c \equiv L/E$ for capture is obtained by imposing $E^2 = \frac{L^2}{r_{\text{ph}}^2} f(r_{\text{ph}})$, i.e.

$$E^2 = f(r_{\text{ph}}) \frac{L^2}{r_{\text{ph}}^2} \Rightarrow b_c^2 \equiv \frac{L^2}{E^2} = \frac{r_{\text{ph}}^2}{f(r_{\text{ph}})}. \quad (23)$$

Now compute $f(r_{\text{ph}})$:

$$f(r_{\text{ph}}) = 1 - \Delta - \frac{2M}{r_{\text{ph}}} = \frac{1 - \Delta}{3}. \quad (24)$$

Therefore,

$$b_c = \frac{\frac{3M}{1-\Delta}}{\sqrt{\frac{1-\Delta}{3}}} = \frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{(1-\Delta)^{3/2}}. \quad (25)$$

In the limit $\alpha = 0$, corresponding to the absence of string cloud effects, the critical impact parameter reduces to $b_c =$

$\frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{(1-\kappa\eta^2)^{3/2}}$. When $\eta = 0$, representing the absence of global monopole effects, the critical impact parameter becomes $b_c = \frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{(1-\alpha)^{3/2}}$. Finally, in the simultaneous absence of both defects, ($\alpha = 0, \eta = 0$), the standard Schwarzschild black hole result is recovered, $b_c = 3\sqrt{3}M$.

D. Weak-field light deflection

For null geodesics we first define the coordinate impact parameter $b_0 \equiv L/E$, where E is associated with the unnormalized Killing vector ∂_t . The treatment parallels weak-field lensing analyses in spacetimes with modified asymptotics and non-Schwarzschild potentials [32, 36, 38]. From (10) with $\varepsilon = 0$,

$$\dot{r}^2 = \frac{1}{1+\ell} \left[E^2 - f(r) \frac{L^2}{r^2} \right] = \frac{E^2}{1+\ell} \left[1 - \frac{b_0^2 f(r)}{r^2} \right]. \quad (26)$$

Using $\dot{\phi} = L/r^2 = b_0 E/r^2$, we compute

$$\left(\frac{dr}{d\phi} \right)^2 = \frac{r^4}{b_0^2(1+\ell)} \left[1 - \frac{b_0^2 f(r)}{r^2} \right], \quad (27)$$

and hence

$$\frac{d\phi}{dr} = \frac{b_0 \sqrt{1+\ell}}{r^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{b_0^2 f(r)}{r^2}}}. \quad (28)$$

The closest approach r_{min} is determined by $dr/d\phi = 0$, implying

$$1 - \frac{b_0^2 f(r_{\text{min}})}{r_{\text{min}}^2} = 0 \Rightarrow b_0^2 = \frac{r_{\text{min}}^2}{f(r_{\text{min}})}. \quad (29)$$

The total deflection angle is

$$\hat{\alpha} = 2 \int_{r_{\min}}^{\infty} \left| \frac{d\phi}{dr} \right| dr - \pi. \quad (30)$$

It is convenient to introduce the asymptotic conical parameter

$$\beta \equiv \sqrt{\frac{1+\ell}{1-\Delta}}, \quad (31)$$

which captures the joint effect of the Lorentz-violating radial rescaling and the defect angle in the asymptotic optical geometry. Since t is not normalized at infinity, the physically normalized impact parameter is defined using $\mathcal{E} = E/\sqrt{1-\Delta}$,

$$b \equiv \frac{L}{\mathcal{E}} = \sqrt{1-\Delta} b_0. \quad (32)$$

In terms of this normalized impact parameter, a systematic weak-field expansion of Eq. (30) gives

$$\hat{\alpha} \simeq \pi(\beta - 1) + \frac{4M}{b} \frac{\sqrt{1+\ell}}{(1-\Delta)^{3/2}} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{M^2}{b^2}\right). \quad (33)$$

The first term is the purely conical contribution, present even when $M = 0$, whereas the second term is the Schwarzschild-like mass contribution dressed by both ℓ and Δ . A detailed perturbative derivation is provided in Appendix A. If one uses the coordinate impact parameter b_0 instead, the mass term is equivalently proportional to $4M\sqrt{1+\ell}/[b_0(1-\Delta)^2]$.

FIG. 4. Weak-field light deflection angle $\hat{\alpha}(b)$ for null geodesics in the bumblebee black hole with dual topological defects. Solid curves show the numerical evaluation of the bending integral in Eq. (30), using $d\phi/dr$ from Eq. (28) and the turning point r_{\min} determined by Eq. (29). Dashed curves depict the leading weak-field approximation in Eq. (33). We fix $M = 1$ and $\ell = 0.2$, and vary the string-cloud parameter α while keeping the monopole scale $\eta = 0.10$ fixed, so that $\Delta(\alpha) = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$ with $\kappa = 8\pi$. The impact parameter b denotes the normalized quantity in Eq. (32); for each α the curve starts outside the capture threshold.

Figure 4 displays the deflection angle as a function of the normalized impact parameter for photons scattered by the effective geometry. For each value of α (equivalently, each $\Delta(\alpha)$)

at fixed η), the numerical result is obtained from the exact bending integral, whereas the dashed curves show the leading weak-field expression. As b/M increases, the numerical curves approach the weak-field prediction, as expected from the condition $M/b \ll 1$. Conversely, for b close to the critical value the weak-field approximation becomes inaccurate and the deflection increases rapidly, signaling proximity to the unstable photon sphere and the onset of capture. Larger α increases Δ and therefore enhances the overall bending through the conical asymptotics encoded in β .

FIG. 5. Weak-field light deflection angle $\hat{\alpha}(b)$ displayed directly as a function of the total deficit parameter Δ . Solid curves correspond to the numerical bending integral in Eq. (30), and dashed curves correspond to the leading approximation in Eq. (33). We use $M = 1$ and $\ell = 0.2$, while treating Δ as the independent parameter. This plot emphasizes that the bending enhancement depends on the total combination $\Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$ appearing in the optical asymptotics.

Figure 5 gives the same weak-lensing comparison in a parameterization where the total deficit Δ is varied directly. For fixed b/M , larger Δ increases both the conical contribution and the dressed Schwarzschild-like mass term in Eq. (33). The numerical curves approach the analytic approximation at large impact parameter, whereas deviations become more pronounced near the capture threshold.

E. Shadow relations for a static observer

Because $g_{tt} \rightarrow -(1-\Delta)$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$, we use the normalized time $\bar{t} = \sqrt{1-\Delta}t$ introduced in Eq. (5). The energy associated with $\partial_{\bar{t}}$ is $\mathcal{E} = E/\sqrt{1-\Delta}$, and the impact parameter defined with normalized energy is

$$\bar{b} \equiv \frac{L}{\mathcal{E}} = \sqrt{1-\Delta} b_0. \quad (34)$$

Thus the critical value becomes

$$\bar{b}_c = \sqrt{1-\Delta} b_c = \frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{1-\Delta}. \quad (35)$$

For a static observer at $r = r_{\text{obs}}$, one may compute the local angle Θ between the photon direction and the radial

direction using an orthonormal tetrad adapted to the static observer, as in standard shadow constructions for static black holes [31, 37, 62, 63]. A standard computation yields

$$\begin{aligned} \sin \Theta_{\text{sh}}(r_{\text{obs}}) &= \frac{\bar{b}_c}{r_{\text{obs}}} \sqrt{\frac{f(r_{\text{obs}})}{1-\Delta}} \\ &= \frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{r_{\text{obs}}} \sqrt{\frac{1-\Delta-\frac{2M}{r_{\text{obs}}}}{(1-\Delta)^{3/2}}}. \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

A corresponding shadow radius can be defined as $R_{\text{sh}}(r_{\text{obs}}) = r_{\text{obs}} \tan \Theta_{\text{sh}}(r_{\text{obs}})$. Notably, ℓ does not enter explicitly in Eq. (36) for static observers: although ℓ rescales the radial sector, it cancels out in the local angle measurement performed by the static tetrad.

For a static distant observer ($r \rightarrow \infty$), the shadow radius is given by

$$R_{\text{sh}} \simeq r_{\text{obs}} \Theta_{\text{sh}} = 3\sqrt{3}(1-\Delta)^{-1} M \quad (37)$$

In the limit $\alpha = 0$, corresponding to the absence of string cloud effects, the shadow radius reduces to $R_{\text{sh}} = \frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{(1-\kappa\eta^2)}$. When $\eta = 0$, representing the absence of global monopole effects, the shadow radius becomes $R_{\text{sh}} = \frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{(1-\alpha)}$. Finally, in the simultaneous absence of both defects ($\alpha = 0, \eta = 0$), the standard Schwarzschild black hole result recovers, $R_{\text{sh}}^{\text{Sch.}} = 3\sqrt{3}M$. Therefore, the presence of dual defects enhanced the shadow radius in comparison to the standard results, that is $R_{\text{sh}} > R_{\text{sh}}^{\text{Sch.}}$.

TABLE I. Photon sphere radius, critical impact parameter, and shadow radius for different limiting cases of the topological defect parameters.

Case	r_{ph}	\bar{b}_c	R_{sh}
$\alpha = 0$	$\frac{3M}{1-\kappa\eta^2}$	$\frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{(1-\kappa\eta^2)^{3/2}}$	$\frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{1-\kappa\eta^2}$
$\eta = 0$	$\frac{3M}{1-\alpha}$	$\frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{(1-\alpha)^{3/2}}$	$\frac{3\sqrt{3}M}{1-\alpha}$
$\alpha = 0 = \eta$	$3M$	$3\sqrt{3}M$	$3\sqrt{3}M$

Figure 6 displays the shadow angular radius for static observers computed from Eq. (36) while varying α at fixed η . In the far-field regime ($r_{\text{obs}} \gtrsim r_{\text{ph}}$), the shadow angle decreases with distance, as expected from geometric scaling, whereas larger α yields systematically larger angular radii at the same r_{obs} . This trend follows from the fact that, in the normalized frame, the critical impact parameter scales as $\bar{b}_c \propto (1-\Delta)^{-1}$ [Eq. (35)], with $\Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$, thereby enhancing the capture cone as the effective deficit grows.

F. Constraints from EHT observations

The shadow relation above can be confronted with the angular diameter inferred by the Event Horizon Telescope (EHT), whose M87* and Sgr A* measurements provide benchmark strong-field tests of compact-object geometry [62, 63].

FIG. 6. Shadow angular radius for a static observer. We plot the angular radius $\Theta_{\text{sh}}(r_{\text{obs}})$ as a function of the observer position r_{obs}/M for representative values of the string-cloud parameter α , keeping the monopole scale η fixed. The effective deficit parameter is $\Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$ with $\kappa = 8\pi$, and Θ_{sh} is computed from the normalized-time shadow relation in Eq. (36). The curves are shown in the far-field domain $r_{\text{obs}} \gtrsim r_{\text{ph}}(\Delta)$ (with r_{ph} given in Eq. (22)), for which Θ_{sh} decreases monotonically with r_{obs} and increases with α (equivalently with Δ) at fixed r_{obs} .

In geometrized units, the observed dimensionless shadow diameter is usually written as

$$d_{\text{obs}} = \frac{D_{\text{src}} \theta_{\text{sh}}}{M_{\text{obs}}}, \quad (38)$$

where D_{src} is the distance to the source, θ_{sh} is the measured angular diameter, and M_{obs} denotes the mass scale used in the observational inference. For the present non-asymptotically flat, deficit-angle geometry, the identification between M_{obs} and the metric parameter M must be stated explicitly. If one identifies the observational mass with the metric parameter M , the theoretical far-field diameter is

$$d_{\text{th}}^{(M)} = \frac{2R_{\text{sh}}}{M} = \frac{6\sqrt{3}}{1-\Delta}, \quad \Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2. \quad (39)$$

Under this metric-mass prescription, positive defect contributions increase the Schwarzschild value $d_{\text{Sch}} = 6\sqrt{3} \simeq 10.392$.

For M87* we adopt the EHT values [62]

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\text{sh}}^{\text{M87*}} &= 42 \pm 3 \mu\text{as}, \\ D_{\text{M87*}} &= 16.8 \pm 0.8 \text{ Mpc}, \\ M_{\text{M87*}} &= (6.5 \pm 0.7) \times 10^9 M_{\odot}. \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

These values give $d_{\text{obs}}^{\text{M87*}} \simeq 11.0 \pm 1.5$. Requiring $d_{\text{th}}^{(M)}$ not to exceed the upper edge of this interval gives the indicative metric-mass bound

$$\Delta \lesssim 1 - \frac{6\sqrt{3}}{12.5} \simeq 0.17. \quad (41)$$

For Sgr A* we use [63]

$$\begin{aligned}\theta_{\text{sh}}^{\text{SgrA}^*} &= 51.8 \pm 2.3 \text{ } \mu\text{as}, \\ D_{\text{SgrA}^*} &= 8277 \pm 9 \text{ pc}, \\ M_{\text{SgrA}^*} &= (4.297 \pm 0.013) \times 10^6 M_{\odot}.\end{aligned}\quad (42)$$

This yields $d_{\text{obs}}^{\text{SgrA}^*} \simeq 9.5 \pm 1.4$. Since $d_{\text{th}}^{(M)} \geq d_{\text{Sch}}$ for $\Delta \geq 0$, the relevant restriction again comes from the upper edge, giving

$$\Delta \lesssim 1 - \frac{6\sqrt{3}}{10.9} \simeq 4.7 \times 10^{-2}.\quad (43)$$

Combining the two sources at this simple one-standard-deviation level therefore suggests, within the metric-mass prescription,

$$\alpha + \kappa\eta^2 \lesssim 0.047.\quad (44)$$

This estimate is useful as an indicative bound on the metric deformation, but it is not a prescription-independent constraint on the defect sector. Indeed, the thermodynamic analysis in Sec. IV shows that the energy conjugate to the normalized Killing time is not simply M . If M_{obs} is instead associated with that first-law energy $U = M/\sqrt{(1+\ell)(1-\Delta)}$, then

$$d_{\text{th}}^{(U)} = \frac{2R_{\text{sh}}}{U} = 6\sqrt{3}\sqrt{\frac{1+\ell}{1-\Delta}},\quad (45)$$

whereas an alternative horizon-length mass $M_h = M/(1-\Delta)$ would give $d_{\text{th}}^{(M_h)} = 6\sqrt{3}$. A rigorous EHT constraint in this spacetime therefore requires a definite mass prescription, together with the full observational likelihood and emission-model systematics.

Table II illustrates the monotonic enhancement of R_{sh}/M as the total defect parameter grows. The entries should be read as metric-parameter values. Their direct interpretation as observational constraints is tied to the mass prescription leading to Eq. (39); other identifications of the observed mass modify the dimensionless diameter as indicated in Eq. (45).

G. Timelike circular orbits and ISCO

For timelike geodesics ($\varepsilon = 1$), the effective potential is treated in the standard way used for circular orbits and marginal stability in spherical black-hole backgrounds [22, 31]. It is

$$V_{\text{eff}}^{(m)}(r) = f(r) \left(1 + \frac{L^2}{r^2} \right).\quad (46)$$

Circular orbits at $r = r_0$ satisfy $\frac{dV_{\text{eff}}^{(m)}}{dr}\big|_{r_0} = 0$. Compute the derivative:

$$\frac{dV_{\text{eff}}^{(m)}}{dr} = f'(r) \left(1 + \frac{L^2}{r^2} \right) + f(r) \left(-\frac{2L^2}{r^3} \right).\quad (47)$$

Setting (47) to zero and simplification results

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{sp}}^2 = \frac{r^3 f'(r)}{2f(r) - r f'(r)} \Big|_{r=r_0}.\quad (48)$$

And the corresponding specific energy

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{sp}}^2 = f(r) \left(1 + \frac{L^2}{r^2} \right) = \frac{2f^2(r)}{2f(r) - r f'(r)} \Big|_{r=r_0}.\quad (49)$$

With $f(r) = 1 - \Delta - 2M/r$ and $f'(r) = 2M/r^2$, we find

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{sp}}^2 = \frac{Mr_0^2}{(1-\Delta)r_0 - 3M}, \quad \text{with } r_0 > \frac{3M}{1-\Delta},\quad (50)$$

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{sp}}^2 = \frac{\left(1 - \Delta - \frac{2M}{r_0} \right)^2}{1 - \Delta - \frac{3M}{r_0}}.\quad (51)$$

The ISCO is obtained from the marginal stability condition $\frac{d^2 V_{\text{eff}}^{(m)}}{dr^2}\big|_{r=r_{\text{ISCO}}} = 0$. Carrying out this calculation (see Appendix B) yields

$$r_{\text{ISCO}} = \frac{6M}{1-\Delta}.\quad (52)$$

In the limiting case $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, which corresponds to the absence of string cloud effects, the ISCO radius reduces to $r_{\text{ISCO}} = \frac{6M}{(1-\kappa\eta^2)}$. Similarly, in the limit $\eta \rightarrow 0$, representing the absence of global monopole effects, the ISCO radius becomes $r_{\text{ISCO}} = \frac{6M}{(1-\alpha)}$. Finally, in the absence of both topological defects, i.e., for $\alpha = 0 = \eta$, one recovers the ISCO radius for the standard Schwarzschild result, $r_{\text{ISCO}} = 6M$. Therefore, Δ shifts the characteristic radii by the scaling factor $(1-\Delta)^{-1}$ relative to Schwarzschild, while ℓ rescales radial evolution through the radial equation (10).

IV. THERMODYNAMICS WITH NORMALIZED ASYMPTOTIC TIME

A. Entropy and horizon area

The horizon area is $A_h = 4\pi r_h^2$, so the Bekenstein–Hawking entropy follows the usual area law [45, 46, 50, 51]:

$$S = \frac{A_h}{4} = \pi r_h^2 = \frac{4\pi M^2}{(1-\Delta)^2}.\quad (53)$$

Figure 7 displays the normalized entropy $S/(4\pi M^2)$ as a function of η for fixed α , with $\Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$. For small η the entropy varies mildly, while it grows sharply as the defect contribution increases and Δ approaches unity. The vertical dotted lines indicate the maximal admissible monopole scale $\eta_{\text{max}}(\alpha)$ determined by the condition $\Delta < 1$. As $\eta \rightarrow \eta_{\text{max}}(\alpha)$ one has $(1-\Delta) \rightarrow 0^+$, and Eq. (53) implies a divergence $S \propto (1-\Delta)^{-2}$, which is emphasized using a logarithmic scale in the vertical axis. Increasing α reduces η_{max} , shifting the divergence to smaller η , consistent with the nonlinear entry of η through $\Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$.

B. Surface gravity and Hawking temperature

For a static metric of the form (1), one may compute the surface gravity using the Killing-horizon definition underlying black-hole thermodynamics [45–47]. In the present coordinates this gives

$$\kappa_H^{(t)} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{f'(r)}{\sqrt{1+\ell}} \Big|_{r=r_h},\quad (54)$$

TABLE II. Illustrative values of $R_{\text{sh}}/M = 3\sqrt{3}/(1 - \Delta)$ for representative values of α and $\kappa\eta^2$. Entries are values of the metric ratio R_{sh}/M and should not be interpreted as independent bounds on α and η .

$\kappa\eta^2(\downarrow)\backslash\alpha(\rightarrow)$	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.10
0.01	5.3022	5.35686	5.41266	5.46963	5.52782	5.58726	5.64799	5.71006	5.77350	5.83837
0.02	5.35686	5.41266	5.46963	5.52782	5.58726	5.64799	5.71006	5.77350	5.83837	5.90472
0.03	5.41266	5.46963	5.52782	5.58726	5.64799	5.71006	5.77350	5.83837	5.90472	5.97259
0.04	5.46963	5.52782	5.58726	5.64799	5.71006	5.77350	5.83837	5.90472	5.97259	6.04204
0.05	5.52782	5.58726	5.64799	5.71006	5.77350	5.83837	5.90472	5.97259	6.04204	6.11312
0.06	5.58726	5.64799	5.71006	5.77350	5.83837	5.90472	5.97259	6.04204	6.11312	6.18590
0.07	5.64799	5.71006	5.77350	5.83837	5.90472	5.97259	6.04204	6.11312	6.18590	6.26042
0.08	5.71006	5.77350	5.83837	5.90472	5.97259	6.04204	6.11312	6.18590	6.26042	6.33677
0.09	5.77350	5.83837	5.90472	5.97259	6.04204	6.11312	6.18590	6.26042	6.33677	6.41500
0.10	5.83837	5.90472	5.97259	6.04204	6.11312	6.18590	6.26042	6.33677	6.41500	6.49519

FIG. 7. Normalized Bekenstein–Hawking entropy $S/(4\pi M^2)$ as a function of the monopole scale η for representative fixed values of the string-cloud parameter α (with $M = 1$). The curves are obtained from Eq. (53) using $\Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$ with $\kappa = 8\pi$. The vertical dotted lines mark the upper bound $\eta_{\max}(\alpha) = \sqrt{(1 - \alpha)/\kappa}$, where $\Delta \rightarrow 1^-$ and the entropy diverges. The y -axis is shown on a logarithmic scale to resolve the rapid growth as η approaches $\eta_{\max}(\alpha)$.

which corresponds to the Killing vector ∂_t . Because t is not normalized at infinity, the physical surface gravity associated with the normalized Killing time \bar{t} is

$$\kappa_H = \frac{\kappa_H^{(t)}}{\sqrt{1 - \Delta}} = \frac{1}{2} \left. \frac{f'(r)}{\sqrt{(1 + \ell)(1 - \Delta)}} \right|_{r=r_h}. \quad (55)$$

Using $f'(r) = 2M/r^2$ and $r_h = 2M/(1 - \Delta)$, we find

$$f'(r_h) = \frac{2M}{r_h^2} = \frac{2M}{\left(\frac{2M}{1 - \Delta}\right)^2} = \frac{(1 - \Delta)^2}{2M}. \quad (56)$$

Therefore,

$$\kappa_H = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(1 - \Delta)^2}{2M} \frac{1}{\sqrt{(1 + \ell)(1 - \Delta)}} = \frac{(1 - \Delta)^{3/2}}{4M\sqrt{1 + \ell}}, \quad (57)$$

and the Hawking temperature $T = \kappa_H/(2\pi)$ becomes

$$T = \frac{(1 - \Delta)^{3/2}}{8\pi M\sqrt{1 + \ell}}. \quad (58)$$

FIG. 8. Normalized Hawking temperature $T(\Delta)$ as a function of the effective deficit parameter $\Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$ for representative values of the Lorentz-violating parameter ℓ (see Eq. (58)). Throughout the plot we fix $M = 1$ and restrict to $0 \leq \Delta < 1$. Increasing Δ suppresses the temperature through the factor $(1 - \Delta)^{3/2}$, while increasing ℓ further reduces T via the prefactor $1/\sqrt{1 + \ell}$.

Figure 8 shows the normalized Hawking temperature as a function of the effective deficit parameter Δ for several values of the Lorentz-violating parameter ℓ . The temperature decreases monotonically with Δ and tends to zero as $\Delta \rightarrow 1^-$, reflecting the strong suppression induced by the conical/defect sector. For fixed Δ , larger ℓ lowers the temperature by rescaling the radial sector, which enters the surface gravity through the factor $1/\sqrt{1 + \ell}$.

C. Thermodynamic energy and first law

Equations (53) and (58) must be supplemented by a thermodynamic energy that is conjugate to the normalized Killing

time. This point is important because the metric parameter M and the horizon-length scale $M/(1-\Delta)$ do not both satisfy the first law with the normalized temperature (58). Let

$$D \equiv 1 - \Delta = 1 - \alpha - \kappa\eta^2, \quad B \equiv 1 + \ell. \quad (59)$$

At fixed (Δ, ℓ) , the area entropy gives

$$dS = \frac{8\pi M}{D^2} dM, \quad (60)$$

whereas the normalized temperature gives

$$T dS = \frac{D^{3/2}}{8\pi M\sqrt{B}} \frac{8\pi M}{D^2} dM = \frac{dM}{\sqrt{BD}}. \quad (61)$$

Therefore the first-law-compatible internal energy is

$$U = \frac{M}{\sqrt{BD}} = \frac{M}{\sqrt{(1+\ell)(1-\Delta)}}. \quad (62)$$

With this identification, the first law at fixed (Δ, ℓ) takes the standard form

$$dU = T dS. \quad (63)$$

This also clarifies the status of the horizon-length parameter $M_h \equiv M/D$: although $r_h = 2M_h$ and $S = 4\pi M_h^2$, M_h is not the energy conjugate to the normalized Hawking temperature when ℓ and Δ are kept fixed.

When the defect parameters are allowed to vary, the first law must include the corresponding work terms. From Eq. (62), or equivalently from $U(S, D) = \sqrt{D/B}\sqrt{S/(4\pi)}$, one obtains

$$dU = T dS + \Psi_\Delta d\Delta, \quad \Psi_\Delta = -\frac{U}{2D} = -\frac{M}{2\sqrt{B}D^{3/2}}. \quad (64)$$

Since $d\Delta = d\alpha + 2\kappa\eta d\eta$, this can be written as

$$dU = T dS + \Psi_\alpha d\alpha + \Psi_\eta d\eta, \quad (65)$$

with

$$\Psi_\alpha = -\frac{U}{2D}, \quad \Psi_\eta = -\frac{\kappa\eta U}{D}. \quad (66)$$

Thus the area law and the normalized temperature are mutually consistent, provided the energy is chosen as in Eq. (62). Conversely, if one insists on using $M_h = M/D$ as the internal energy, the first law would require an entropy different from the area law,

$$S_{(M_h)} = \frac{4\pi\sqrt{B}M^2}{D^{5/2}} + \text{const.}, \quad (67)$$

which is not the Bekenstein–Hawking entropy (53). In the present effective-metric treatment we therefore keep $S = A_h/4$ and use U as the thermodynamic energy. If the metric is embedded in a specific nonminimally coupled bumblebee action, the same conclusion should be checked independently with Wald’s entropy formula.

D. Heat capacity and Helmholtz free energy

At fixed (Δ, ℓ) , Eqs. (53), (58), and (62) imply $S \propto U^2$ and $T \propto 1/U$. Eliminating U shows $S \propto 1/T^2$, as in the Schwarzschild canonical ensemble, and hence [47, 53]

$$C = T \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial T} \right)_{\Delta, \ell} = -2S = -\frac{8\pi M^2}{D^2} = -\frac{8\pi B U^2}{D}, \quad (68)$$

which is negative, indicating canonical instability.

The Helmholtz free energy in the normalized frame is then defined by

$$F \equiv U - TS. \quad (69)$$

Using Eqs. (53), (58), and (62), one finds

$$TS = \frac{U}{2}, \quad F = \frac{U}{2} = \frac{M}{2\sqrt{(1+\ell)(1-\Delta)}}. \quad (70)$$

Thus the free energy is finite throughout $0 \leq \Delta < 1$ and diverges only at the limiting boundary $\Delta \rightarrow 1^-$ for fixed metric parameter M . The expression (70) replaces the horizon-length diagnostic $M_h - TS$; the latter may still be plotted as a geometric diagnostic, but it should not be called the thermodynamic Helmholtz free energy unless M_h is adopted as the internal energy together with a correspondingly modified entropy.

FIG. 9. Thermodynamic Helmholtz free energy $F(\Delta)$ in the normalized-time frame, obtained from Eq. (70). We plot $F/M = 1/[2\sqrt{(1+\ell)(1-\Delta)}]$ for representative values of the Lorentz-violating parameter ℓ and fixed $M = 1$. The free energy grows as $\Delta \rightarrow 1^-$ because of the defect-induced redshift factor, while increasing ℓ suppresses F through the factor $1/\sqrt{1+\ell}$.

Figure 9 shows the corrected Helmholtz free energy associated with the first-law energy U . The qualitative behavior differs from the horizon-length diagnostic $M_h - TS$: at fixed M and Δ , larger ℓ lowers F , consistently with the suppression of both the normalized temperature and the thermodynamic energy by the same radial bumblebee factor. The divergence as $\Delta \rightarrow 1^-$ occurs only at the boundary of the admissible parameter domain.

V. THERMODYNAMIC FLUCTUATIONS AND INFORMATION GEOMETRY

Thermodynamic fluctuations can be characterized geometrically by the Ruppeiner metric in the entropy representation. This approach descends from Weinhold’s thermodynamic metric and Ruppeiner’s fluctuation theory and has

been widely applied to black-hole ensembles and phase transitions [54–61, 64–68]. In the entropy representation we use

$$g_{ab}^{(R)} = -\frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial X^a \partial X^b}, \quad X^a = (U, \eta), \quad (71)$$

while keeping the string-cloud parameter α and the Lorentz-violating parameter ℓ fixed. The use of U , rather than the metric parameter M , is essential: U is the energy selected by the normalized first law in Sec. IV C. A Hessian constructed with (M, η) probes a non-conjugate parametrization of the family of solutions and can introduce degeneracies that should not be interpreted as invariant thermodynamic singularities. As usual for asymptotically flat black holes with negative heat capacity, the Hessian metric is not positive definite in the canonical sense. We therefore use the scalar curvature as a diagnostic of the thermodynamic geometry rather than as a probability metric for a globally stable canonical ensemble.

A. Entropy as a function of (U, η) and the Ruppeiner metric

Using $M = U\sqrt{BD}$, with $D = 1 - \alpha - \kappa\eta^2$ and $B = 1 + \ell$, the area entropy becomes

$$S(U, \eta) = \frac{4\pi BU^2}{1 - \alpha - \kappa\eta^2}, \quad \kappa = 8\pi. \quad (72)$$

Direct differentiation yields the nonvanishing Ruppeiner metric components

$$g_{UU}^{(R)} = -\frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial U^2} = -\frac{8\pi B}{D}, \quad (73)$$

$$g_{U\eta}^{(R)} = -\frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial U \partial \eta} = -\frac{16\pi B\kappa U\eta}{D^2}, \quad (74)$$

$$g_{\eta\eta}^{(R)} = -\frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial \eta^2} = -\frac{8\pi B\kappa U^2(1 - \alpha + 3\kappa\eta^2)}{D^3}. \quad (75)$$

The fluctuation line element is therefore

$$ds_R^2 = g_{UU}^{(R)} dU^2 + 2g_{U\eta}^{(R)} dU d\eta + g_{\eta\eta}^{(R)} d\eta^2. \quad (76)$$

The determinant is

$$\det(g^{(R)}) = \frac{64\pi^2 B^2 \kappa U^2}{D^3}, \quad (77)$$

which is nonzero throughout the physical domain $D > 0$ for $U > 0$ and $\kappa > 0$. Hence the first-law-compatible two-dimensional fluctuation metric has no finite degeneracy locus in the allowed parameter range.

B. Ruppeiner scalar curvature

A key scalar diagnostic is the Ruppeiner curvature R_R associated with $g_{ab}^{(R)}$. For the two-dimensional state space (U, η) at fixed (α, ℓ) , a direct computation from Eqs. (73)–(75) yields

$$R_R(U, \eta) = -\frac{1 - \alpha}{4\pi BU^2} = -\frac{(1 - \alpha)(1 - \Delta)}{4\pi M^2}. \quad (78)$$

The curvature is negative for $\alpha < 1$, which is automatically satisfied inside the physical domain $\Delta < 1$ with $\kappa\eta^2 \geq 0$. It is regular for all finite η satisfying $0 \leq \eta < \sqrt{(1 - \alpha)/\kappa}$ and

has no analogue of the locus $1 - \alpha - 3\kappa\eta^2 = 0$ that appears if one builds the Hessian with the non-conjugate coordinate M . The negative sign indicates an effectively attractive statistical interaction in the usual information-geometric terminology [56, 57, 60], while the absence of a finite curvature singularity shows that the minimal first-law-compatible ensemble does not by itself contain a phase-transition signal.

FIG. 10. Ruppeiner scalar curvature as a function of the monopole scale η in the first-law-compatible thermodynamic geometry. The plotted quantity is $M^2 R_R$, obtained from Eq. (78) after rewriting the result in terms of the metric parameter M , namely $M^2 R_R = -(1 - \alpha)(1 - \alpha - \kappa\eta^2)/(4\pi)$. We set $\kappa = 8\pi$ and show representative values of the string-cloud parameter α . The curves are negative and regular over the physical interval, with no finite singularity or degeneracy locus.

Figure 10 displays the corrected curvature profile. If U is kept fixed, Eq. (78) is independent of η ; the plotted η dependence appears because the same scalar has been rewritten in terms of the metric parameter $M = U\sqrt{(1 + \ell)(1 - \Delta)}$. In either representation the curvature remains smooth in the physical domain and approaches zero as $\Delta \rightarrow 1^-$ at fixed M . This regular behavior replaces the artificial divergence obtained from the non-conjugate Hessian in the variables (M, η) .

For completeness, Appendix C gives the determinant and curvature calculation. The result also clarifies the role of thermodynamic coordinates: the scalar curvature is meaningful only after the energy entering the first law has been fixed. Establishing a genuine phase transition would require an extended thermodynamic phase space or an independent response function that becomes singular, for example after including charge, pressure, rotation, or independent defect potentials [52, 53, 69, 70].

VI. CONCLUSION

We have investigated a Schwarzschild-like black hole in bumblebee gravity endowed with two topological defects, namely a cloud of strings and a global monopole. In the effective geometry considered here, both defects enter through the single combination $\Delta = \alpha + \kappa\eta^2$, whereas the Lorentz-violating bumblebee parameter ℓ rescales the radial sector.

This separation makes it possible to identify which observables are controlled by the conical/defect structure and which are directly sensitive to Lorentz-symmetry breaking.

For the geodesic sector we derived the radial equations, the Binet-type orbital equation, the photon-sphere radius, the critical impact parameter, the weak-field deflection angle, the static-observer shadow relation, and the ISCO radius. The horizon, photon sphere, and ISCO obey the common scaling $r_h : r_{\text{ph}} : r_{\text{ISCO}} = 2M : 3M : 6M$ multiplied by $(1 - \Delta)^{-1}$. Thus the defect sector pushes all characteristic radii outward without changing their mutual ratios. The normalized shadow radius is likewise enhanced, $R_{\text{sh}}/M = 3\sqrt{3}/(1 - \Delta)$, while ℓ cancels from the static local shadow angle. By contrast, the weak deflection angle contains both a conical contribution, $\pi[\sqrt{(1 + \ell)/(1 - \Delta)} - 1]$, and a mass-induced contribution rescaled by $\sqrt{1 + \ell}(1 - \Delta)^{-3/2}$.

A comparison with the EHT angular diameters of M87* and Sgr A* suggests that the combination $\alpha + \kappa\eta^2$ is the relevant metric deformation for shadow observables. If the observational mass is identified directly with the metric parameter M , the one-standard-deviation upper ranges give the indicative bound $\alpha + \kappa\eta^2 \lesssim 0.047$. However, this bound is mass-prescription dependent. If the observed mass is instead associated with the thermodynamic energy $U = M/\sqrt{(1 + \ell)(1 - \Delta)}$, or with a horizon-length scale $M/(1 - \Delta)$, the theoretical dimensionless shadow diameter changes. A robust observational analysis must therefore specify the mass definition appropriate to the non-asymptotically flat geometry.

In the thermodynamic sector we emphasized that the time coordinate must be normalized at infinity because $g_{tt} \rightarrow -(1 - \Delta)$ rather than -1 . With this normalization, the Hawking temperature is suppressed according to $T = (1 - \Delta)^{3/2}/(8\pi M\sqrt{1 + \ell})$, whereas the area entropy is enhanced as $S = 4\pi M^2/(1 - \Delta)^2$. These two quantities satisfy the first law provided the internal energy is chosen as

$$U = \frac{M}{\sqrt{(1 + \ell)(1 - \Delta)}}. \quad (79)$$

When the defect sector is allowed to vary, the first law acquires the work terms $\Psi_\alpha d\alpha + \Psi_\eta d\eta$, with potentials given in Eq. (66). At fixed (Δ, ℓ) , the heat capacity remains negative, $C = -2S$, showing that the canonical instability of the Schwarzschild black hole persists. The thermodynamic Helmholtz free energy in the normalized frame is $F = U/2 = M/[2\sqrt{(1 + \ell)(1 - \Delta)}]$.

Finally, we constructed the Ruppeiner geometry for the minimal state space (U, η) at fixed string-cloud parameter α and fixed Lorentz-violating parameter ℓ . The first-law-compatible Hessian metric has determinant

$$\det(g^{(R)}) = \frac{64\pi^2(1 + \ell)^2\kappa U^2}{(1 - \alpha - \kappa\eta^2)^3}, \quad (80)$$

and scalar curvature

$$R_R = -\frac{1 - \alpha}{4\pi(1 + \ell)U^2} = -\frac{(1 - \alpha)(1 - \Delta)}{4\pi M^2}. \quad (81)$$

Therefore the fluctuation geometry is curved and negative in the physical domain, but it has no finite singular locus. The singularity that arises from a Hessian built with (M, η) is consequently best understood as an artifact of using a non-conjugate thermodynamic coordinate rather than as a phase-transition signal. A natural continuation of this work would

be to extend the phase space by including charge, a cosmological constant/pressure, rotation, or independent defect potentials; in such enlarged ensembles one can test whether curvature singularities align with conventional heat-capacity divergences, spinodal curves, or critical points, following the logic of black-hole chemistry and thermodynamic topology [52, 53, 67, 68, 71]. Another useful direction would be to perform a full likelihood analysis of EHT observables and weak-lensing data to separate the effects of α , η , and ℓ beyond the simple prescription-dependent bounds obtained here [36, 38, 62, 63].

Appendix A: Weak-field deflection: normalization and expansion

This appendix summarizes the weak-field expansion used in Sec. III D. For null geodesics we define the coordinate impact parameter

$$b_0 \equiv \frac{L}{E}, \quad (A1)$$

where E is the conserved energy associated with the coordinate time t . The radial equation gives

$$\frac{d\phi}{dr} = \frac{b_0\sqrt{1 + \ell}}{r^2} \left(1 - \frac{b_0^2 f(r)}{r^2}\right)^{-1/2}, \quad (A2)$$

with $f(r) = 1 - \Delta - 2M/r$. The turning point is determined by

$$b_0^2 = \frac{r_{\text{min}}^2}{f(r_{\text{min}})}. \quad (A3)$$

Thus the total bending angle is

$$\hat{\alpha} = 2 \int_{r_{\text{min}}}^{\infty} \left| \frac{d\phi}{dr} \right| dr - \pi. \quad (A4)$$

The asymptotic part of the optical geometry is conical. Its opening is encoded by

$$\beta = \sqrt{\frac{1 + \ell}{1 - \Delta}}. \quad (A5)$$

When $M = 0$, the bending angle reduces to the purely conical contribution

$$\hat{\alpha}_0 = \pi(\beta - 1). \quad (A6)$$

Keeping the first correction in $M/b_0 \ll 1$ gives

$$\hat{\alpha} \simeq \pi(\beta - 1) + \frac{4M\sqrt{1 + \ell}}{b_0(1 - \Delta)^2} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{M^2}{b_0^2}\right). \quad (A7)$$

Because $g_{tt} \rightarrow -(1 - \Delta)$ at infinity, the normalized time is $\bar{t} = \sqrt{1 - \Delta}t$ and the corresponding energy is

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{E}{\sqrt{1 - \Delta}}. \quad (A8)$$

The physical impact parameter is therefore

$$b \equiv \frac{L}{\mathcal{E}} = \sqrt{1 - \Delta} b_0. \quad (A9)$$

Substituting $b_0 = b/\sqrt{1 - \Delta}$ gives the expression used in the main text,

$$\hat{\alpha} \simeq \pi(\beta - 1) + \frac{4M}{b} \frac{\sqrt{1 + \ell}}{(1 - \Delta)^{3/2}} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{M^2}{b^2}\right). \quad (A10)$$

Appendix B: ISCO condition from the circular-orbit angular momentum

For completeness we show how Eq. (52) follows from the marginal-stability condition. For a static spherical metric with $f(r) = 1 - \Delta - 2M/r$, the specific angular momentum of a timelike circular orbit at radius r_0 is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{sp}}^2(r_0) = \frac{Mr_0^2}{(1 - \Delta)r_0 - 3M}. \quad (\text{B1})$$

The marginally stable circular orbit is obtained equivalently from $d^2V_{\text{eff}}^{(m)}/dr^2 = 0$ or from the minimum of $\mathcal{L}_{\text{sp}}^2(r_0)$. Differentiating Eq. (B1) gives

$$\frac{d\mathcal{L}_{\text{sp}}^2}{dr_0} = \frac{Mr_0 [(1 - \Delta)r_0 - 6M]}{[(1 - \Delta)r_0 - 3M]^2}. \quad (\text{B2})$$

The nonzero solution is therefore

$$r_{\text{ISCO}} = \frac{6M}{1 - \Delta}, \quad (\text{B3})$$

which reduces to the Schwarzschild value $6M$ when the defect sector is switched off.

Appendix C: Ruppeiner curvature for the first-law state space (U, η)

In this appendix we provide the essential intermediate steps leading to Eq. (78). Define

$$A \equiv 1 - \alpha, \quad D(\eta) = A - \kappa\eta^2, \quad B = 1 + \ell, \quad (\text{C1})$$

so that

$$S(U, \eta) = 4\pi BU^2 D^{-1}. \quad (\text{C2})$$

Using the definition (71), the nonvanishing components are those quoted in Eqs. (73)–(75). Their determinant is

$$\det(g^{(R)}) = \frac{64\pi^2 B^2 \kappa U^2}{D^3}. \quad (\text{C3})$$

This determinant does not vanish in the physical domain $D > 0$ for $U > 0$. A direct computation of the Christoffel symbols and the two-dimensional Ricci scalar gives

$$R_R(U, \eta) = -\frac{A}{4\pi BU^2}. \quad (\text{C4})$$

Restoring $A = 1 - \alpha$ yields Eq. (78). In terms of the metric parameter $M = U\sqrt{BD}$, the same result is

$$R_R = -\frac{(1 - \alpha)D}{4\pi M^2} = -\frac{(1 - \alpha)(1 - \Delta)}{4\pi M^2}. \quad (\text{C5})$$

Thus the first-law-compatible fluctuation geometry is regular throughout the finite physical range of η .

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